

THEORETICAL PRINCIPLES OF USING STYLES OF SINGING SCHOOLS IN TEACHING THE SCIENCE OF "TRADITIONAL SINGING"

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Abstract. *The given article presents information regarding theoretical foundations of using the methods of singing schools in teaching "Traditional Singing", the heritage of professional music in the oral tradition, perfected in the Uzbek musical heritage.*

Keywords: *tradition, professional music, pedagogy, style, music, singing, singing, performance, pedagogical necessity, professional music education, traditional singing.*

It is important to suggest that listening, studying and mastering the richest traditions of performing singers' works with its methodological support is of great importance in teaching the science of traditional singing. After all, the effective use of the performing style and performing school, the methodological experience of previous generations requires great skill and experience from the teacher of musical and theoretical subjects of higher educational institutions. This school of skill is transmitted to the student empirically due to its continuity. Therefore, if the methodological provisions are not fully recorded, it is impossible to achieve quality and effectiveness in teaching the science of traditional singing, as a result, its traditional flavor will disappear. The theory and practice of singing still have the traditional experience of singing schools. However, today's globalization process, world development, and acceleration of information exchange make it possible to apply effective methods and means of teaching traditional singing in practice. Searching for perfect and effective methods of teaching hymn singing, as well as their reasonable use, will help ensure the effectiveness of the work.

Definitely, scientists of the CIS E.A. Bazhenov, E.M. Barvinskaya, N.V. Goretskaya, V.V. While studying the scientific works of Kudryavtseva and others, it was noted that the theoretical and methodological foundations of teaching "traditional singing performance" to future music teachers in Russia are not sufficiently formed. This process allows us to emphasize that vocal pedagogy in the CIS countries remains an empirical topic. Some researchers (V.V. Emelianov) have developed and substantiated the initial stage of teaching traditional singing, subject to singing based on the phonopedic method, its coordination is limited to practice.

Definitely, the performance of Uzbek traditional singers is distinguished not only by its wide scope, such performance scenes as *dyna*, *miyonkhat*, *dunasr*, *avch* and *furovard*, but also by unique styles in foreign musical performance. While mastering such schools of performance, students are required to develop new skills, improve their knowledge, performance skills, master the technology of sound production and the technology of performance ethics. Another pedagogical aspect of the traditional singing method is that it is based on extralinguistic phenomena of the utterance function, ensuring the transition from speech and voice to the formation and development of professional performing traditions [3]. Shows students how to effectively work with students with low vocal abilities. Restoring the painful point of sound is important due to the range and timbre integration of the performance parts.

However, continuous singing according to this method leads to a strong expansion, deep design of the singing sound, which negatively affects the process of voice formation. This method is based on step-by-step training in traditional singing pedagogy.

Surprisingly, singing sets in motion the natural physiological state of the body. The result of any method of teaching singing to undergraduate students is full-voiced, free, muscleless singing, with a clear direction of sounds, which contributes to a beautiful, bright timbre of the voice. On the contrary, this is a search for a paradigm of singing, natural beauty and naturalness of the voice.

Let's look at the unique features of vocal training of another researcher. A.G. Menabeni offers a methodology for the initial stage of teaching solo singing, describes in detail the voice of adults and children, emphasizes the need to perform exercises to tune the voice in a specific genre, in order to form a singing voice and skills in performing the school repertoire. [2].

While teaching traditional singing in the field of preschool music education, we take into account the features of the singing training of students and the components of their singing skills. They are expressed in the following components, including:

- motivational-voluntary component includes attention to performing activity and emotional-volitional preparation for a public performance;

- operational-technological component includes the acquisition of skills: hearing, sound production, breathing, includes the dynamics of the introduction, mionkhat, dunasr, avj and furovard of singing;

- regulatory-emotional-volitional component is aimed at improving the skills of self-management of executive actions, self-regulation in professional development, the ability to overcome technical difficulties in performance;

- individual-creative component reflects the individual-creative nature of the activity [5].

The methodology of teaching traditional singing performance to undergraduate students by analyzing and comparing works, components and elements of traditional singing training and their methodological support are insufficiently developed and made it possible to determine the presence of a number of unfounded technical problems. In particular, the absence of the "individual performance" method in teaching traditional singing in the field of music education in the field of pedagogy. It would not be an exaggeration to say that N.B. Gontarenko's research was devoted to solving the problem we posed. Based on his own experience, the scientist puts forward the experience of "solo singing", in which he proposes to remove psychophysiological clamps and effectively use the "intensive method" in the methodological experience of vocal teachers.

In our opinion, in the context of teaching students the science of traditional singing, opening the voice, developing diction and articulation, working on the middle climax and culminating curtain of the song, as well as improving stylistic skills, the method of the work, and the technique of performance is the most individual activity, if it is carried out through training, then the development and performance of the work will be more perfect. The method we propose allows using the vocal apparatus and diction problems of the student to teach traditional singing [4]. Based on the study of the creative experience of many years of traditional singing performance schools, they describe the principles of their voice formation: breathing, sound attack, work on vowels, voice only by the rational method, i.e. on the basis of highly developed breathing recommends singing freely, ensuring constant freedom of movement of the larynx [7]. The principles of sonority are used in teaching traditional singing by practicing performer S.

Mannopov, but he does not mean the elements, which are upright posture, traditions that arose in the performing styles of the singing school, but about the one used in vocalization, shows the positions and registers of free singing in the middle avj, avj curtain. This is achieved through regular development of professional training to improve the artistic and creative potential of performance, which ensures the process of developing traditional singing skills in students. The artistic and performing potential of student singers should be a category that has a rational and emotional basis, the possibility of realizing the personality in the future in the context of independent creative activity in performing Uzbek folk traditional songs [1].

Certainly, in the context of professional music in the oral tradition of the Uzbek people, songs created by composers are proposed to be performed in their original form by representatives of the next generation on the basis of a comprehensive program. The methodology of the future teacher takes into account the age and individual characteristics of students, their interests, value directions, aimed at deep artistic and creative disclosure of the personality, but the technical component in it is necessary for the formation of traditional singing skills of the student.

Additionally, the future music teacher will master the basics of the formation of the traditional singing voice, vocal apparatus, methodological instruments, in the performing and methodological experience (traditions) accumulated over many years of traditional singing performance, must have the basics of scientific understanding and generalization of vocal and performing skills. pedagogical process. The original roots of the tradition of teaching traditional singing go back to the 9th-12th centuries. This performance was formed within the framework of local singing performance schools, the dynamics of which depended on the development of singing genres and, above all, the traditions of professional musical performance in the Uzbek folk oral tradition. Changes in the creative searches of local composers manifested themselves in classical performing genres, styles, trends and forms, which required singers to reveal the wide possibilities of song performance technique and the artistic tasks corresponding to them. It is important to understand that this process is continuous and is formed by the efforts of many composers, performers, teachers, various singers, representatives of performing and pedagogical schools. The conditional result of this work literally laid the foundation for today's path of great development of Uzbek traditional singing schools. By the middle of the 17th century, the beauty of these singing schools led to a number of improvements in high-performance models in the Khan's palaces and in front of the general public. These formations manifested themselves in the classical singing tradition, which is distinguished by the following characteristics: bright, light and high styles. While performing traditional singing, perfect control of the voice, impeccable cantilena, honed sophistication of sound, virtuoso coloratura, melody with an emotional climax are required.

What do we really need to understand by the traditional school of singing? There are many schools, scientific schools, traditional and non-traditional schools that have reached our time and continue their activities. As a traditional school of singing, we focused on the existence of the following main aspects:

It is not a secret that the concepts of "composer", "performer", "listener", "singer", "traditional singer", "school" are logically close to each other in terms of topic and are mutually integrating;

-compositional tradition and its mutual influence on later performing traditions, as well as the tradition of this singing tradition of representatives of the next generation;

-formation, development, acceptance by the general public of the style and school tradition of traditional singing performance;

-improvement of professional Uzbek folk music and improvement of its performance methods, influence on its traditional appearance, i.e. its formation as a school;

-progressive methodological ideas, teaching and performance methods that improve the development of the technical component and its emotional and artistic component, the study of traditional singing.

At present time the concept of school is widely used as a fundamental concept and is of great importance in the social life of the population.

Speaking about the school phrase, one of the local scientists K. Panjiiev suggested that "in Ancient Greece, during the period when the slave system was collapsing and giving way to the era of feudal fragmentation, all people wanted to learn to read and write, and other workers of the lower class worked 10-12 hours a day. However, they also really wanted to read and write. During such a period, they used lunchtime for classes only in reading and writing. This time was also called school. He puts forward the idea that school is used in the sense of free time from work. In the explanatory dictionary of the Uzbek language, the term "school" is used in the meaning of a place where students are taught to read and write under the guidance of a teacher. In addition, scientists often associate this concept with general pedagogy, education, upbringing and upbringing of the younger generation. This concept is used in a broad sense. From the scientists of the CIS, let us remind the definition suggested by V.A. Deryajni, in a broad sense "school is the definition of certain creative directions in science, literature, art; in a narrow sense: a school of playing the piano, violin" [6]. For further explaining the same idea, singing requires a separate school of singing compared to other areas of art [4]. The school itself is an organized group of one or another style of performance, which is formed by a subject with a high ability to personalize, transmitted through continuity in the direct interaction of the teacher and student in the learning process, a system of artistic creativity, musical-aesthetic, performing principles and methods of work created by them [5]. The main aspects of the study we conducted are the didactic framework, as well as the methods and techniques created by singing schools.

It is known to everyone that the process of research it is important to explain such a concept as "school of composition". School of composition is a community that combines a common combination of a high level of training in the spheres of social life, developed professional musical culture, national artistic value, unique features of the creative individuality of the composer, professional musical education, style, genre, form, etc. collection. School of composition influences the traditional school of singing, determines and forms its path. School of composition is an artistic direction based on certain creative principles or a representative group of students and followers of a composer. Composers actually create in one voice. Therefore, their school is distinguished by melodiousness, musical rhythm and color-rhythmic features. There is also a school of polyphonic artists, known mainly as the "school of composition" and defined as a general description of the polyphonic professional musical production of the country [5]. If we talk about the patterns of formation of traditional singing schools in Uzbek folk music, we can say without a doubt that there is a connection between musical style, language, genre, form, and performance features of singing performance schools [3]. In such a process, singing performance has a significant impact on the content of the pedagogical school. Performance practice has always

determined the tasks of teaching, professional training, and preparing singers for performance in concert programs.

Certainly, learning to perform a song requires students to strictly adhere to the principles of an individual approach. In a singing school where there is a continuity of technology and methods for studying ashula performance, the transfer of the basics of performing technique and artistic and performing professional and creative experience from generation to generation serves to improve the innovations of musical and pedagogical traditions. The influence of the development of Uzbek music on the formation of different national singing schools goes back to the performing schools of our ancestors. It is known to everyone that Turgun Alimatov, a representative of the famous school of musical performance on tanbur instruments, "a set of technical means for singing performance, ensuring a high level of playing on traditional musical instruments, a unique standard of sound and style of performance in the Uzbek national culture" goes back to the traditional performance of national singing schools, defined [4]. According to local scientists Dr.R. Yunusov, the following knowledge occupies a special place in mastering the traditional singing library. In particular, this is the content of the poetic text of the work, performance (technical and artistic tone), concert and performance skills (free and high-quality performance of the work from memory on stage) and the master-student tradition (studying and performing the work together with the master). Music educators Dr.K. Pandjiev note that the pedagogical component of the Uzbek traditional singing school is "targeted training, musical education, a set of principles and methods of teaching, historically changing professional and pedagogical activity." In all cases affecting the development of the performing arts of the singing school, it is important to adhere to a certain system of transmitting a certain pedagogical experience in the process of education and training [7].

Surprisingly, in our research work, the concept of a traditional singing school was considered in a broad and narrow sense. In a broad sense, national traditions with their language, centuries-old culture, temperament, social origin, nature, environment, etc., as well as professional national musical culture, local musical style, singing schools, national school of composition and performing arts are an existing national value. In a narrow sense, a school is the definition of teaching principles, the formation of skills under the guidance of a teacher, the performing and methodological (unique) experience of traditional singing, the bearer of the traditions of the student-student, and the independent work of the student-successor is an activity.

In the course of the study, based on the characteristics of the traditional singing school, we divided it into two sections: traditional singing performance and singing pedagogy.

The school of traditional singing performance is a set of components and educational elements formed in the traditions, means of musical expression corresponding to the national singing school, aimed at achieving the level of performing skills. The school of singing pedagogy represents the continuity of methods and styles of vocal training, aimed at mastering the components and elements of the traditional singing school, and determines the foundations of musical professional training. The pedagogical school of singing depends on two features: the phonetics of the language of a certain people and the performance requirements of the genre.

The emergence of the performing school is directly related to the development of the composing school and, in particular, to the development of the singing genre. The features of the ashul dramaturgy and the creative relationships of composers determine the tasks of singing performance, form the methodological principles of educating ashul performers. For the evaluation

the history of traditional singing performance and music pedagogy, it is possible to trace the evolution of national singing performance of a particular country. The history of the opera genre and the emergence of the traditional singing school begins at the end of the 16th century, in the late Renaissance. At that time, Italy consisted of a number of city-states, hence the name of the vocal schools: Florence, Rome, Venice, Naples and Bologna. Each vocal school contributed to the development of vocal art. Later, these schools are known as the only Italian vocal school of bel canto, in which periods of the formation of the performing style are observed, the performing standard of the performer's singing corresponding to each period is formed; Performing and methodological traditions, concepts, elements and methods of teaching, etc. appear and develop.

In the further development of singing, the life and creative path of performers, formed in the school of singing performance, is of great importance. In the work of traditional Uzbek singers (T. Jalilova, Arif Alimaxumova, Komiljon Otaniyazov, Otajon Khudoyshukurov, Rakhmatjon Kurbanov) new forms of solo singing, two-part and three-part forms of singing appeared. The method of singing in this way, the transition of the styles of performance binni, flower, ishkom, which were previously in the singing style of Uzbek folk oral professional music, to new forms led to a change in the technique of singing performance and, accordingly, to the improvement of the technique of singing in the vocal apparatus.

In traditional singing, due to wide intervals, the song goes to its entrance, it becomes more complex and is polished again, reaching the successful result. Performers of singing schools are required to pronounce words well, paying attention to the features that correspond to the entire complex of voice, facial expressions, gestures, mouth movements, musical and scenic expressive means. In the same way, among foreign scientists, F. Cavalli in his works singled out expressive recitatives, arias and arias. The science of sound Legato promotes the idea that singing skills should be developed on the basis of demonstrating vocal works. At the same time, the researcher says that in his studies the vocal-melodic principle is developed, and puts forward the point of view that arias are widespread, the vocal range is expanded by two octaves, and interval relationships are complicated. The composer often used vocals that require skill and strength. All these innovations complicated the technical requirements for vocalists, which led to a search for new stylistic ideas.

Similarly, A. Scarlatti wrote about the importance of various arias (lamento, buffone, virtuoso), secco and recitatives of the accompaniment in operas in the library of European traditional singing. In addition, the researcher developed types of arias in the operas of Seria: aria of complaint, aria of revenge (anger), heroic aria, pastoral, aria of bravura. He also noted that the main thing in the serial opera, which widely used in vocal works. The skill of the singer was the ability to change and improvise the 2nd part of the aria da capo. If we turn to the history of the Uzbek traditional school of singing, then a system of improving the professional activities of students in choral performance and teaching solo performance appeared. The first musical performers were skilled performers of that time, teachers selected students according to their performing abilities, and if necessary, taught them to study music at home, learn singing, participate in various wedding ceremonies, performing creative concerts. opportunities to test their skills. The rapid development of secular music occurred in the 9th-15th centuries at the highest stage of development of oral professional music. In addition, he determined the direction of the then Uzbek national music performing school. In addition to the existing schools of mastery in music pedagogy, accumulated over many years, he brought a deeper and more honest expressiveness to the school of singing performance. In the second quarter of the 18th century,

during the period of increasing feudal fragmentation in the territory of Uzbekistan, the gains of reforms almost diminished in the performance of traditional singing music. Usually there are changes in the performance of instruments, for example, warming up the circle, providing accompaniment of the ensemble of instruments depending on the content and tonality of the performance of each piece, different rhythms in performance, enhancing the beauty and melody of the performance. technical performance, for example, a complex manner of singing ensured the formation of a unique school [5]. Composers created remarkable stereotypical chants with extended virtuoso cadenzas for castrati singing. The art of voice control was assessed only by the technique of voice control and the ability of the performer to improvise ornaments in the voice corresponding to the content of the poem.

During these periods, there is an addition of strong young voices, the appearance of performers of this genre in large performing schools, the use of pedagogical conditions in the formation of new styles and voice capabilities in the contingent of performers when performing the previous song created opportunities. While studying the topic of the research, the Republic showed that the performance of traditional singing can be divided into three groups:

These are: Bukhara-Samarkand school of traditional singing performance;
Fergana-Tashkent school of traditional singing performance;
Khorezm school of traditional singing performance.

It is known to everyone that each of these performing schools has formed its own local musical traditions. Dialect is of particular importance in it. At the same time, the most important of them is the methodical improvement of performance, the continuity of the singer's creativity from generation to generation. Clarity of pronunciation of vowel sounds, breathing technique, smoothness of register [1].

However, the art of traditional singing in the first quarter of the 19th century, a number of traditions formed in the school of traditional singing, has its own performing style, an important criterion for the formation of singing skills in performance, as well as voice, diction, lamentation. What is a veil, that opened up new performing directions for singing many vowels due to their unique euphony [3].

In teaching traditional singing, the singing genre of musical art is considered as a genre of great importance. The singing genre is a high achievement of national art in its melodic structure, including elements of vocalization. In addition to the fact that this is a unique genre of Uzbek oral creativity, requiring high professional and pedagogical skills from the performer, it is characterized by wide breathing tones, which leads to melodiousness. It contains the source of cantilena - the basis of the art of singing. Features of professional music in folk oral tradition are characterized by psychologism and a holistic connection between word and music. In order to introduce students to such high performing traditions, special knowledge, extensive knowledge and pedagogical experience in teaching students are necessary. This is not grace, but an integral part of the tone, its essence. The direction of music education requires pre-university students to understand and truly feel the ornaments of the singing genre, as well as to develop professional methodological and performing skills in students when teaching the science of traditional singing. Music pedagogy and the system of its teaching to undergraduate students, who are considered future music teachers, not only praising specific performance traditions, but also their own voice, timbre, range, language, dialect and even vowels, but also in order to further ease their emotional and spiritual burden, meaning, feeling, content of words requires disclosure by means of pedagogical conditions.

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